

Methods of Purposeful English Teaching: Analysis and Results

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the methods of purposeful English teaching and evaluates their effectiveness. English has become a widely used and global language of communication around the world today. Therefore, it is very important to choose effective methods in teaching English. The article discusses the main methods used in teaching English, such as the communicative approach, the direct method, the audiolinguistic method, and private curricula. By comparing these methods with teaching practice and changes in the education system, the article attempts to evaluate effective strategies for teaching English and their results. As a result of the article, recommendations are made to identify the most effective methods of teaching English and to widely introduce them in the education system.*

Keywords: *Teaching methods, purposeful teaching, communicative approach, direct method, audiolinguistic method, effective methods, educational strategies, pedagogical approach.*

Introduction: English is currently taught as a second or third language in many countries around the world. Globalization, economic relations, and progress in the fields of science have made learning English a necessity. However, choosing the right approach and method is of great importance for effective teaching of English. The methods used in the teaching process vary depending on factors such as the level of language learning of students, the characteristics of the learning environment, and the skills of the teacher.

Identifying effective methods of teaching English will not only help students improve their language skills, but also develop their independent learning and communication skills. In this context, this article aims to analyze various methods of teaching English and assess their effectiveness. In order for the teaching process to be more effective, there is a need to integrate different methods and try new innovative approaches. Throughout the article, traditional and modern methods of teaching English, their strengths and weaknesses are analyzed. English is widely used as a global communication language today, and is taught as a second or third language in many countries. The process of learning and teaching English, at the same time, is developing on the basis of rapidly changing educational methods and pedagogical approaches. The development and implementation of understandable and effective English teaching methods is of great importance in the development of students' language skills.

Targeted teaching methods, that is, approaches aimed at using the language in practice and real-life situations, serve to increase the effectiveness of the language learning process. Therefore, it is necessary to analyze the methods used in teaching English, to study how they affect students and what results they produce. This article analyzes the main methods used in teaching English, such as the communicative approach, the direct method, the audiolinguistic method and modern innovative approaches. Based on this, recommendations are given on identifying effective methods of teaching

English and applying them in a way that suits the needs of students. The article attempts to show scientific and practical approaches that will help effectively guide students in learning English.

Material and methods: Choosing effective methods of targeted teaching of English is necessary for students to achieve success in the language learning process. The methods used in the teaching process play an important role in teaching all aspects of the language: listening, reading, writing and speaking. By analyzing the main methods used in teaching English, assessing their effectiveness and showing the positive and negative aspects of each method, the article explores the possibilities of effectively organizing language learning.

The communicative approach is one of the most effective methods of teaching English. This method implements language learning through communication in real-life situations. Students learn the language by applying it in practice, which significantly increases their language skills. Based on this method, the teacher does not just teach certain grammatical rules in the process of language learning, but also teaches students to express their thoughts in real communication.

In this method, students are taught to communicate directly in English. Basically, grammar and word formation are learned only through speaking and listening. This method helps to learn the language quickly, but sometimes it can cause difficulties in understanding the rules of grammar.

The audiolinguistic method pays special attention to listening and pronunciation in teaching English. In this method, students develop speaking skills by listening to the language. This approach can be particularly effective in teaching pronunciation. However, there are some limitations to this method, such as students having difficulty learning grammar and writing.

Nowadays, the use of proprietary learning programs and technologies in English language teaching is also widespread. Interactive materials, online lessons, and mobile applications have expanded the possibilities for learning the language. These methods allow students to learn at their own pace and in a way that suits their individual needs.

Integrating several methods in English language teaching can be effective, namely, combining the communicative approach, the audiolinguistic method, and the direct method. This approach allows students to develop all language skills at the same time.

Result and discussions: When choosing effective methods of teaching English, it is important to consider the advantages and disadvantages of each method. The communicative approach and the integrated approach greatly help develop students' abilities to use the language in practice and in real life. The direct method and the audiolinguistic method can give students quick and effective results in learning the language. However, each method should be effective depending on its context.

The implementation of the methods presented in the article into the education system will increase the effectiveness of innovative approaches to teaching English and make the language learning process more effective for students. When choosing language learning methods for teachers and educational institutions, it is necessary to take into account their compliance with the needs, language levels and goals of students.

An analysis of the methods of targeted teaching of English showed the effectiveness of various methods for students. Each method has its own advantages and limitations. The communicative approach allows students to use language in practice, in real-life situations, which is effective in strengthening students' language skills. The direct method gives quick results, but can cause difficulties in understanding grammar in depth. The audio-linguistic method, while useful in developing pronunciation and listening skills, can lead to shortcomings in learning grammar and writing.

New technologies and innovative methods, such as interactive lessons and online resources, allow students to learn the language individually. An integrated approach is effective in developing all language skills of students by combining several methods. Thus, the most effective methods of teaching English should be selected in accordance with the needs and goals of each student.

Conclusion: When choosing English teaching methods, the effectiveness of each method depends on the language level of the students, their personal needs and the teaching context. Communicative approaches and integrated methods are of particular importance in developing students' abilities to use language in real life. Audiolingual and direct methods help to accelerate the language learning process, but in some cases they can hinder the sufficient development of grammar and writing skills.

To successfully teach students English, teachers need to integrate different methods and choose an approach that is appropriate for the learning style of students. The introduction of modern pedagogical approaches and technologies in the education system allows for more effective results in teaching English. Also, developing students' independent work and self-learning skills in the language learning process increases their language learning success.

REFERENCES

1. Saodat Parkhadjanovna Saidakbarova, Nargiza Komiljonovna Mukhamedova, Iroda Makhmudjanovna Jalolova, Zulfiya Olimjonovna Mirabdullayeva, & Dilfuza Abduganiyevna Akramkhodjayeva. (2024). The Role Of Speech Genres In The Communication Process. *Educational Administration: Theory and Practice*, 30(5), 2500–2503. <https://doi.org/10.53555/kuey.v30i5.3304>
2. Saidakbarova, Saodat Parkhadjanovna, et al. "The Role Of Speech Genres In The Communication Process." *Educational Administration: Theory and Practice* 30.5 (2024): 2500-2503.
3. Tursunova V. B. HISTORY OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING METHODS //SCIENTIFIC ASPECTS AND TRENDS IN THE FIELD OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH. – 2024. – T. 2. – №. 20. – С. 97-100.
4. Komiljonovna M. N. Texnika Universiteti talabalariga ingliz tili darslarida loyixa tashkil etish tizimi //Хоразм Маъмун Академияси ахборотномаси. – 2021. – С. 80-82.
5. Mukhamedova Nargiza Komiljonovna. Interactive teaching methods- the basic of innovative educational technologies// Хоразм Маъмун Академияси ахборотномаси. 2019/3/12.- Б.7
6. NASRETDINOVA, M. N., MAXMUDOVA, U. F., & MANSUROVNA, B. M. (2024). FICTION AND THE STUDY OF THE CONCEPT OF ELLIPSIS.
7. Mansurovna, Bahrombekova Munisa. "Modern methods of teaching foreign language." *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal* 12.1 (2022): 27-31.
8. Mansurovna, Bahrombekova Munisa. "Goals of Teaching Foreign Languages." *Journal of Higher Education and Academic Advancement* 1.1 (2024): 208-210.
9. Khusamiddinova M. M., Alimbayeva S. A. SCIENTIFIC AND METHODOLOGICAL ISSUES OF ORGANIZING ONLINE COURSES //SCIENTIFIC ASPECTS AND TRENDS IN THE FIELD OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH. – 2024. – T. 2. – №. 20. – С. 90-93.
10. Rakhmanberdiyeva, K. S., Tadjiyeva, M. D., Bahrombekova, M. M., & Artikova, L. S. (2023). Technologies Of Organizing Independent Education In Teaching Students Foreign Languages (In The Case Of Non-Philological Universities). *Boletin de Literatura Oral-The Literary Journal*, 10(1), 4005-4010.
11. Abdullayeva, M., & Maxmudova, M. (2022). IMPORTANCE OF LEGAL EDUCATION CHARACTERISTICS. *Science and Innovation*, 1(7), 1311-1314.
12. Kasimova, S. S. (2024). Transformation of phrases and its destructions. *Salud, Ciencia y Tecnología-Serie de Conferencias*, 3, 740-740.